

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7810474>

UDK 50

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF COMPLICATED RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF MATERIALS UNDER LARGE DEFORMATION

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Annotation: In this work, the problem of hydrostatic compression of a single spherical continuity defect is solved, and all irreversible deformations are attributed to the creep phenomenon. A certain difficulty lies on this path in that in the vicinity of a micro defect, the deformations are always large and, therefore, the entire consideration should be carried out within the framework of the model of unsteady creep at large deformations. The theory of large elastoplastic deformations constructed in [3] and the power law of creep are taken as the basis for constructing this model.

Keywords: stress, large deformations, creep, viscoelasticity, relaxation, elasticity

МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ СЛОЖНЫХ РЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ СВОЙСТВ МАТЕРИАЛОВ ПРИ БОЛЬШИХ ДЕФОРМАЦИЯХ

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Аннотация: В данной работе решается задача о гидростатическом сжатии единичного сферического дефекта сплошности, а все необратимые деформации относят к явлению ползучести. Определенная трудность на этом пути заключается в том, что вблизи микродефекта деформации всегда велики и поэтому все рассмотрение следует проводить в рамках модели нестационарной ползучести при больших деформациях. За основу построения этой модели взяты теория больших упругопластических деформаций, построенная в [3], и степенной закон ползучести.

Ключевые слова: напряжение, большие деформации, ползучесть, вязкоупругость, релаксация, упругость

Metals, like all structural materials, have creep properties in a certain range of stresses and temperatures. Even at room temperature, conventional structural steels or aluminum alloys exhibit limited creep properties. The small size of defects, even under moderate external loads, leads to irreversible deformation of the material in their vicinity and to the appearance of internal residual stresses, which also significantly affect the long-term strength of products. In this case, at least irreversible deformations in the vicinity of continuity defects cannot be considered small.

Previously [1], it was shown that, within the framework of such a theory of large elastoplastic deformations, with an ideal character of plastic flow, the effect of adaptability of single continuity defects to cyclic loads of the “load–unload” type is observed. That is, after each unloading, the dimensions of the defect do not change, as well the level and distribution of strains and stresses. Taking into account the rheological properties of the material should lead out of such a situation. However, it turned out [2] that taking into account the viscous properties of materials at the stage preceding the plastic flow or at the stage of unloading leads to a significant decrease in the size of the defect compared to that observed in the case of ideal plasticity, but when using the model of a viscoelastic-plastic medium, stress relaxation does not manifest itself in the process of unloading. To study this phenomenon, a model of the medium is proposed taking into account large deformations, when all irreversible deformations are referred to as creep deformations.

Let us take as a basis the model of large elastoplastic deformations [3], the main kinematic relations of which in the direct Cartesian system of spatial (Euler) coordinates can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{De_{ij}}{Dt} &= \varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{ij}^p - \frac{1}{2} \left((\varepsilon_{ik} - \varepsilon_{ik}^p + z_{ik}) e_{kj} + e_{ik} (\varepsilon_{kj} - \varepsilon_{kj}^p - z_{kj}) \right) \\ \frac{Dp_{ij}}{Dt} &= \varepsilon_{ij}^p - p_{ik} \varepsilon_{kj}^p - \varepsilon_{ik}^p p_{kj}, \quad \frac{Dn_{ij}}{Dt} = \frac{dn_{ij}}{dt} - r_{ik} n_{kj} + n_{ik} r_{kj} \\ \varepsilon_{ij} &= \frac{1}{2} (v_{i,j} + v_{j,i}), \quad v_i = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + v_m u_{i,m} \\ r_{ij} &= w_{ij} + z_{ij} (e_{ij}, \varepsilon_{ij}), \quad w_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} (v_{i,j} - v_{j,i}) \\ d_{ij} &= e_{ij} + p_{ij} - \frac{1}{2} e_{ik} e_{kj} - e_{ik} p_{kj} - p_{ik} e_{kj} + e_{ik} p_{km} e_{mj} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In relations (1), u_i, v_i are the components of the vectors of displacements and velocities of the points of the medium; e_{ij} and p_{ij} are the reversible and irreversible components of the Almansi total strain tensor d_{ij} ; $\frac{D}{Dt}$ – objective time derivative of tensors; the source ε_{ij}^p in the equation of tensor variation p_{ij} is the tensor of irreversible strain rates, $z_{ij} = -z_{ij}$ is the non-linear part of the rotation tensor, fully written out in [3], which determines its difference from the rigid rotation tensor w_{ij} .

Following the formalism of nonequilibrium thermodynamics, stresses in a medium are completely determined by reversible strains, and for the considered case of an incompressible medium, these dependences are written as

$$\sigma_{ij} = -p_1 \delta_{ij} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial e_{ik}} (\delta_{kj} - e_{kj}). \quad (2)$$

In relations (2) p_1 is the additional hydrostatic pressure, W is the elastic potential, which for an isotropic medium is taken in the form

$$\begin{aligned} W &= (a - \mu) J_1 + a J_2 + b J_1^2 - k J_1 J_2 - \zeta J_1^2, \\ J_1 &= e_{jj} - \frac{1}{2} e_{ij} e_{ji}, \quad J_2 = e_{ij} e_{ji} - e_{ij} e_{jk} e_{ki} + \frac{1}{4} e_{ij} e_{jk} e_{ks} e_{si}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here $\lambda, \mu, a, b, \theta$ are the elastic moduli of the medium.

We accept that the components of the irreversible strain rate tensor are related to the stress components by the Norton creep law [4 – 8].

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{ij}^p &= \frac{dV(\Sigma)}{d\sigma_{ij}}, \quad V(\Sigma) = B \Sigma (\sigma_{ij})^n \\ \Sigma &= \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} ((\sigma_1 - \sigma)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma)^2)}^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad \sigma = \frac{\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{3}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here B and n are given constants, $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ are the principal values of the stress tensor.

Within the framework of the model of large deformations described above, the problems of the behavior of the boundary of a spherical micro defect (micropore) under conditions of operational loads were solved.

Consider a ball of initial radius R_0 with a single spherical continuity defect (micropore) of initial radius r_0 at the center of the ball. The deformation process is specified by the boundary conditions

$$\sigma_{rr}|_{r=R(t)} = -P(t), \sigma_{rr}|_{r=s(t)} = 0 \tag{5}$$

where σ_{rr} is the radial component of the stress tensor in the spherical coordinate system $r, \varphi, \theta, R(t) \gg r_0$ is the radius of the spherical surface on which the external pressure is set, $s(t)$ is the current radius of the micropore boundary.

The kinematics of the medium according to the accepted incompressibility condition is determined up to an unknown function $\varphi(t)$:

$$u_r = r - (r^3 + \varphi(t))^{1/3}, \varphi(t) = s_0^3 - s^3(t) = R_0^3 - R^3(t) \tag{6}$$

where $u = u_r$ is the only non-zero component of the displacement vector.

According to formulas (2) and (3), the stress components, up to an unknown function of the additional hydrostatic pressure, are calculated depending on

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{rr} = & -p_1 + g_1 e_{rr} + g_2 e_{rr}^2 - g_3 e_{rr} e_{\theta\theta} + g_4 e_{rr}^3 + g_5 e_{rr} e_{\theta\theta}^2 + g_6 e_{rr}^2 e_{\theta\theta} - g_7 e_{rr}^4 + \\ & + g_8 \left(e_{rr} e_{\theta\theta}^4 - 4 e_{rr} e_{\theta\theta}^3 + 2 e_{rr}^2 e_{\theta\theta}^3 - \frac{1}{2} e_{rr}^2 e_{\theta\theta}^4 \right) - g_9 e_{rr}^2 e_{\theta\theta}^2 + g_{10} \left(3 e_{rr}^5 - \frac{1}{2} e_{rr}^6 \right) + \\ & + 2g_{11} \left(e_{rr}^4 e_{\theta\theta} + 2 e_{rr}^3 e_{\theta\theta}^2 - 4 e_{rr}^3 e_{\theta\theta} - \frac{1}{2} e_{rr}^4 e_{\theta\theta}^2 \right), \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\theta\theta} = & -p_1 + g_1 e_{\theta\theta} + g_{12} e_{\theta\theta}^2 - \frac{1}{2} g_3 e_{rr} e_{\theta\theta}^2 + g_{13} e_{\theta\theta}^3 + g_{18} \left(e_{\theta\theta}^5 - \frac{1}{6} e_{\theta\theta}^6 \right) + \\ & + g_{11} \left(\frac{1}{4} e_{rr}^4 e_{\theta\theta}^2 - 2 e_{rr}^3 e_{\theta\theta} + \frac{1}{2} e_{rr}^4 e_{\theta\theta} - e_{rr}^3 e_{\theta\theta}^2 \right) + g_{15} e_{rr} e_{\theta\theta}^2 - g_{16} e_{\theta\theta}^4 + \\ & + g_{14} e_{rr}^2 e_{\theta\theta} - g_{17} e_{rr}^2 e_{\theta\theta}^2 + g_8 \left(2 e_{rr}^2 e_{\theta\theta}^3 + e_{rr} e_{\theta\theta}^4 - \frac{1}{2} e_{rr}^2 e_{\theta\theta}^4 - 4 e_{rr} e_{\theta\theta}^3 \right), \end{aligned}$$

$$g_1 = 2\mu, g_2 = \mu + 4a + 4b + 2k, g_3 = 4(2b + k),$$

$$g_4 = 4 \left(a + b + 2k + \frac{3}{2}\zeta \right), g_5 = 2(2b + 3k + 12\zeta), g_6 = g_5 + 4k,$$

$$g_7 = a + b + \frac{19}{2}k + 9\zeta, g_8 = k + 6\zeta, g_9 = 2b + 7k + 24\zeta, g_{10} = \frac{3}{2}(k + \zeta),$$

$$g_{11} = k + 3\zeta, g_{12} = \mu + 4a + 8b + 4k, g_{18} = 9(k + 2\zeta),$$

$$g_{13} = 4(a + 2b + 4k + 6\zeta), g_{14} = \frac{1}{2}g_5 - 6\zeta, g_{15} = \frac{1}{2}g_6 + 12\zeta$$

$$g_{16} = a + 2b + 19k + 36\zeta, g_{17} = b + \frac{7}{2} + 15\zeta, p_1 = P - \frac{\partial W}{\partial J_1}.$$

The components of total strains are found from the known displacement field (6) by the relations

$$d_{rr} = \frac{1}{2}(1 - H^{-4/3}), d_{\theta\theta} = d_{\varphi\varphi} = \frac{1}{2}(1 - H^{2/3}), H = 1 + \frac{\varphi(t)}{r^3}, \quad (8)$$

$$d_{\theta\theta} = \frac{1}{2}\left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-2d_{rr}}}\right).$$

According to kinematic dependences (1), we have

$$\varepsilon_{rr}^p = \frac{dp_{rr}}{dt}(1 - 2p_{rr})^{-1}, \varepsilon_{\theta\theta} = \frac{dp_{\theta\theta}}{dt}(1 - 2p_{\theta\theta})^{-1},$$

$$e_{rr} = 1 - x^{-\frac{2}{3}}, e_{\theta\theta} = 1 - x^{\frac{1}{3}}, x = \left(\frac{1-2p_{rr}}{1-2d_{rr}}\right)^3 = H^4(1 - 2p_{rr})^3. \quad (9)$$

Substituting (8) and (9) into constitutive relations (4) leads to the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dp_{rr}}{dt}(1 - 2p_{rr})^{-1} &= Bn\Sigma^{n-1}\left(1 - H^{-\frac{8}{3}}(1 - 2p_{rr})^{-2}, 1 - H^{\frac{1}{3}}(1 - 2p_{rr})\right) \\ \Sigma(a, b) &= g_1(a - b) - g_2a^2 + g_{12}b^2 + g_4a^3 - g_{13}b^3 + \frac{1}{2}g_3\left(\frac{1}{2}ab^2 - ab\right) + \\ &+ g_{19}\left(a^2b - \frac{1}{2}a^2b^2\right) + g_{10}\left(3b^5 - \frac{1}{2}a^6\right) + \frac{1}{3}g_{18}\left(\frac{1}{2}a^6 - 3b^5\right) - g_7a^4 + \\ &+ \frac{3}{4}g_{11}\left(a^4b + 2a^3b^2 - \frac{1}{2}a^4b^2 - 4a^3b\right) + g_{16}b^4 \\ g_{19} &= 2b + 7k + 18\zeta \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) at each point of the medium $s(t) \leq r \leq R(t)$ is an ordinary differential equation for calculating the irreversible strain component p_{rr} (or $p_{\theta\theta}$). On the other hand, the stress components are found by integrating the equation of motion

$$\sigma_{rr,r} + 2\frac{\sigma_{rr} - \sigma_{\theta\theta}}{r} = -\rho_0\left(\frac{\dot{\varphi}(t)}{3r^2} + \frac{2}{9}\frac{\dot{\varphi}^2(t)}{r^5}\right),$$

using the second boundary condition (5). Having calculated the stresses at the outer boundary according to the first boundary condition (5), we obtain an integrodifferential relationship between the loading pressure $P(t)$ and the function $\varphi(t)$

$$P(t) = 2 \int_{s(t)}^{R(t)} \frac{N(e_{rr}, e_{\theta\theta})}{r} dr - \rho_0\left(\frac{\dot{\varphi}(t)}{3}\left(\frac{1}{R(t)} - \frac{1}{s(t)}\right) + \frac{\dot{\varphi}^2(t)}{18}\left(\frac{1}{R(t)^4} - \frac{1}{s(t)^4}\right)\right). \quad (11)$$

Let us present the numerical results of the calculations. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the changes in the loading force and the micropore boundary, respectively. Until the time $\tau_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\rho_0 R_0}} t$, the sample is actively loaded, at which, given the increasing loading force $P(t)$, solving the integrodifferential system of equations (10–11), we find the unknown function $\phi(t)$ and the distribution of irreversible strains p_{rr} . Starting from the moment $\tau_1 = 15$, we consider several options for the development of the process of deformation of the material of the medium. Then the initial conditions for equations (10 – 11) will be the parameters of the stress-strain state at $\tau = \tau_1$.

Figure 1 – Change in loading force $\frac{P(\tau)}{\mu}$

Under number 1 (solid line) in Fig. 1 and 2 show the process of unloading the material of the sample, when the loading force first decreases and becomes equal to 0 at the moment $\tau = 30$, and after that, it remains free from external pressure for some time. The stress relaxation process (2, dotted line) corresponds to a constant total strain field, and the redistribution of reversible and irreversible components necessarily causes

a decrease in the stress level in the body. If we fix the loading force and follow the behavior of the micro defect boundary along this path (3, dash-dotted line), it turns out that the cavity radius gradually decreases, i.e. in the vicinity of the defect, the creep process of the material begins.

Figure 2 – Change in cavity radius $s(\tau)$

The proposed model of the process of nonlinear creep at large deformations is based on the model of large elastoplastic deformations, in which the division of total deformations into reversible and irreversible components is a consequence of understandable thermodynamic principles, which is a significant advantage of the applied approach. The solved problems of creep, stress relaxation, and unloading in a ball with a single spherical continuity defect are aimed at describing the experimentally known process of micropore healing. It is shown that the constructed model of large elastic-creep deformations satisfactorily describes the processes of material creep under active loading and the subsequent process of residual stress relaxation.

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Поступила в редакцию 01.03.2023

Принята к публикации 16.03.2023

Для цитирования:

Pham Thi Thuy, Nguyen Minh Hue, Ha Nguyen Thuy Linh, Truong Thi Dung Mathematical modeling of complicated rheological properties of materials under large deformation // Инновационные научные исследования. 2023. № 3-1(27). С. 13-21. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>